

Infra-Red Spectra of 2, 5-Dihydroxyacetophenone

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On reviewing the spectral data it has been observed that much work has been done on substituted benzenes¹⁻³, phenols^{4,5}, acetophenones⁶, 2-hydroxyacetophenones^{7,8}, hydroquinones^{9,10} by various workers. We are reporting now the infra-red spectra of 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone recorded on Perkin Elmer 421 in KBr matrix and nujol mull.

The close resemblance of the compound with the reported ones earlier makes the comparison easier.

Compound (V) is having comparable structure with those of compounds (I) to (IV) taken together. In their recent communication Misra and Pande¹¹ have reported the values for 2,5-diacetyl hydroquinone (VI)

which is structurally very much similar to the compound reported here.

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Combining both the spectra, *i.e.*, in KBr and nujol the following assignments may be made :

Hydrogen bonding : 3300–2858 cm^{-1} (weak); Phenyl ring stretching : 1738 cm^{-1} (weak); ν (CO) out of plane : 1618 cm^{-1} (sharp); C–C stretching : 1584 cm^{-1} (sharp); C–C stretching : 1561 cm^{-1} (weak); C–C stretching : 1542 cm^{-1} (sharp); C–C stretching : 1498 cm^{-1} (sharp); –(OH) phenolic : 1408 cm^{-1} (sharp); Methyl : 1372 cm^{-1} (sharp); C–H bending : 1268 cm^{-1} (weak); ν (C–O–) asymmetric : 1253 cm^{-1} (medium); = C–CO–R stretching : 1217 cm^{-1} (sharp); = C–C–C stretching : 1214 cm^{-1} (sharp); ν C–O stretching : 1021 cm^{-1} (medium); β (= CH) in plane : 968 cm^{-1} (sharp); (OH) in plane : 789 (sharp); (OH), ν (= CH) out of plane : 738 (sharp).

The deviations in the shifts may be attributed to the various factors like hydrogen bonding, presence of carbonyl groups¹², conjugate-chelate system¹³, etc., conjugation of C = C to the C = O group gives rise to typical shifts in the infrared, the C = O band going to the region (1618 cm^{-1}) and C = C to (1584–1498 cm^{-1}) with sharp and weak bands. Hydrogen bonding due to hydroxyl group in position two and acetoxy-carbonyl group in one has a visible effect on these shift deviations while hydroxyl in position five may be considered to be non-affecting¹².

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